

English Version

What is this survey about?

This survey is about tourism, High Nature Value rural landscapes, your opinions about biodiversity, and other nature-related concepts.

How long does it take to complete the questionnaire?

Completing it takes approximately 35 minutes.

What are we aiming for?

We aim to observe the factors that influence people's intention to have a biocultural experience in a High Nature Value rural landscape. This study is part of the BIOTraCes project supported by Horizon Europe of the European Union. This study has been approved by an independent ethics committee, specifically the ethics committee of Babes-Bolyai University, Cluj-Napoca.

Rights and obligations of respondents

The beneficiary of your responses does not have access to your identifying data; for them, your responses are anonymized. All information about your rights, obligations, and GDPR data protection is included in your contract with Talk Online.

Purple text contains instructions and it will not be included in the questionnaire for the respondents. Answers to all questions are required, unless otherwise specified. Please ignore the text highlighted in purple or blue.

1) Have you taken trips in the last 5 years to rural areas in Romania (with or without High Nature Value)?

1= No, 2=Yes [one choice]

2) How much time per year do you spend in the countryside (whether you live there, are visiting, on vacation, for work, or for any other reason)? (Please write the number of days per year) [open answer]

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High Nature Value (HNV) rural landscapes are located in rural areas where traditional agriculture is the main economic activity and a key factor in nature conservation. These lands are characterized by the presence of natural and semi-natural vegetation, generally permanent pastures that may have never been ploughed. They usually exhibit a great diversity of species and are integrated into an extensive and uninterrupted mosaic landscape that includes natural elements such as field edges, hedgerows or stone walls, wooded areas or shrubs, streams, patches of cultivated land, and orchards. High

Nature Value rural landscapes represent over 30% of the total agricultural area in Romania: 5 million hectares, associated with small-scale (semi-subsistence) farms, usually family-owned, in the hill areas inside and outside the Carpathian arc.

From now on, this questionnaire mainly refers to visiting High Nature Value rural landscapes for the purpose of having a biocultural tourist experience. We will call this activity a "biocultural tourist experience in High Nature Value rural landscapes."

Biocultural tourism can be a lever for both the sustainable development of rural communities and the protection of High Nature Value rural landscapes. The biocultural aspect refers to the fact that people enjoy both the beauties of nature and the socio-cultural values (traditions, monuments, etc.).

3) Have you heard of High Nature Value (HNV) rural landscapes before?

1= No, 2=Yes [one choice and if 2 is selected, "3.1)" must be answered; if 1 is selected, they do to "4)"]

3.1) Where did you hear about High Nature Value (HNV) rural landscapes? [open answer]

.....

4) Have you visited High Nature Value (HNV) rural landscapes before?

1= No, 2=Yes [one choice]

5) How interested are you in visiting High Nature Value (HNV) rural landscapes in the next 12 months for the biocultural tourist experience they offer? Select a value between 1 and 7, where 1 = Not interested at all, ..., 7 = Very interested. [one choice]

1= Not interested at all, 2,3,4,5,6, 7= Very interested

6) How long have you been interested in visiting High Nature Value rural landscapes? Please write the number of years.

.....

7) How do you usually visit High Nature Value rural landscapes? You can select multiple answers. [multiple choice]

1. Alone
2. With family
3. With friends
4. With organized groups
5. On pilgrimages
6. With colleagues
7. I have never visited them

8. Others. Please specify which

8) How often have you visited High Nature Value rural landscapes in the past 5 years? [one choice]

1=Never

2= Less than once a year or once a year

3= Twice a year

4= Three times a year

5= Four times a year or more

9) What are your sources of information for choosing a vacation destination? You can select multiple answers. [multiple choice]

a) Online booking platforms. If you selected this option, write which platforms you use most often:

b) Social media pages

c) Recommendations from friends

d) Recommendations from travel agencies

Others. Please specify :

10) What are the main reasons you visit/wish to visit High Nature Value rural landscapes? Indicate how important each of them is to you in determining whether to visit High Nature Value rural landscapes. Select a value between 1 and 7, where 1 = Not important at all, ..., 7 = Very important [matrix; one choice for each line]

a) Peace and quiet

b) Local cultural events (festivals, fairs)

c) Nature in general

d) For large carnivores (bears, wolves) (to observe them)

e) Beauty of the cultural-natural landscape

f) Experience of traditional practices

g) Local food

h) Local drinks

i) For sport, exercise

j) Interaction with local people

k) Supporting the local community through my visit

l) Contributing to nature conservation through my visit

m) Visiting cultural heritage (houses, churches, fortresses, bridges, architecture)

- n) Therapeutic purpose
- o) Collecting mushrooms, berries, medicinal plants
- p) To learn as an ordinary person, not as a scientist (about people, places, plants, etc.)
- q) For research purposes, as a scientist, professor, or student
- r) For work purposes
- s) Volunteering
- t) Relaxation without a specific goal

11) If you have other reasons for visiting High Nature Value rural landscapes, please list them below. [\[open answer\]](#)

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12) From all the reasons mentioned, write down the top three most important ones that motivate you to visit a High Nature Value rural landscape for a biocultural experience. [\[open answer\]](#)

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13) When you visit High Nature Value rural landscapes, what do you DISLIKE about the experience, what causes you discomfort or fear?
[\[matrix; one choice for each line\]](#)

1= Very low fear/discomfort, ..., 7= Very strong fear/discomfort

- a) Fear of large carnivores (bears, wolves)
- b) Fear of other wild animals (snakes, boars, etc.)
- c) Fear of shepherd dogs
- d) Fear of insects (spiders, mosquitoes, wasps, horseflies, etc.)
- e) Fear of stray dogs on the streets, hills, etc.
- f) Fear of poor food hygiene
- g) Lack of infrastructure for indoor water
- h) Lack of quality drinking water
- i) Lack of a private bathroom in the room where you are staying
- j) Unpaved, muddy roads
- k) Fear of damaging your car due to road conditions
- l) Fear of allergies due to old things in the house
- m) Aggressive, drunk people
- n) Lack of food options

- o) Lack of accommodation options
- p) Lack of potable/quality drinking water
- q) Lack of options for activities, risk of getting bored
- r) Parasites (ticks, fleas, etc.)
- s) Fear of getting lost
- t) Fear of not having phone signal
- u) Fear of not having internet
- v) High prices
- w) Bad weather
- x) Electric fences
- y) Lack of authentic traditional products (e.g., food)
- z) Excessive presence of cars in the village
- aa) Excessive noise (music, etc.), inappropriate behaviour of locals or tourists
- bb) I don't have time to visit High Nature Value rural landscapes
- cc) Too high prices
- dd) Lack of interest from those who accompany me on trips (family, friends) in High Nature Value rural landscapes

14) If there are other factors that bother or concern you, please write them down below.

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15) Among all the reasons mentioned, which are the most significant and prevent you from visiting (or visiting more frequently) a High Nature Value rural landscape for a biocultural experience?

.....

16) Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 = Strongly disagree, ..., 7 = Strongly agree
 [matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) The economic model needs to be changed to better integrate nature conservation and agricultural production in High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- b) Profit in High Nature Value rural landscapes should be maximized by adopting intensive agriculture.
- c) Biodiversity should be protected only in protected areas, and not on land used for agricultural production.

Biodiversity = all life types found in a given area. It encompasses the variety of animals, plants, fungi, and even microorganisms such as bacteria that make up our natural world. Each of these species and organisms works together in ecosystems, like a complex network, to maintain balance and support life. Biodiversity supports everything we need from nature in order to survive: food, clean water, health remedies, and shelter. Biodiversity also includes less visible aspects such as genes, plant varieties, or animal breeds produced through cultural selection throughout history. The diversity of ecosystems, landscapes, and, not least, the diversity of High Nature Value rural landscapes also falls under the category of biodiversity.

- d) Biodiversity is a key support for agricultural production, and therefore it should be maintained on all agricultural lands. DV2
- e) Nature-friendly agriculture helps in adapting to climate change.
- f) Adapting to climate change can only be achieved through the use of modern technology, because nature cannot adapt on its own.
- g) Adapting to climate change is not necessary because the climate changes are not dramatic.
- h) Consuming local products is crucial for maintaining nature-friendly agricultural practices and the biodiversity of High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- i) Traditional agriculture and nature-friendly farming practices are often the result of poverty and the lack of options available to those who practice them.
- j) In the context of a free market, it is acceptable for small farmers to disappear if they are not economically competitive.
- k) Small farmers and local producers should be financially supported, culturally accepted, and motivated because they are crucial for the identity and uniqueness of our rural landscapes.
- l) Intensive (industrial) agriculture is the best way to address world hunger.
- m) Too much attention is given to small farmers and producers, while industrial production feeds the world.
- n) Organic, local, and seasonal products are essential for sustainable consumption.
- o) Conventional products (i.e., those that are not traditional or organic) offer a better guarantee of food quality than foods from High Natural Value areas.
- p) The government should reduce the amount of money invested in environmental policy and invest elsewhere.
- q) Agricultural policies and subsidies for farmers should be maintained as agriculture is a strategic sector.
- r) Agricultural subsidies should be granted to farmers based on their level of production.

17) Do you believe that the biocultural experience of tourists in a High Nature Value rural landscape contributes to the protection of the local natural environment? 1 = Contributes very little, ..., 7 = Contributes very much [one choice]

18) Do you believe that the biocultural experience of tourists in a High Nature Value rural landscape contributes to the preservation of the socio-cultural values of the area (traditions, monuments, etc.) [one choice]

1= Contributes very little, ..., 7= Contributes very much

19) Do you believe that the biocultural experience of tourists in a High Nature Value rural landscape contributes to the economic development of the area? [one choice]

1= Contributes very little, ..., 7= Contributes very much

20) How would you characterize your experience with biocultural tourism in High Nature Value rural landscapes? [one choice for each line]

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- a) 1= It is very unpleasant for me, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7= It is very pleasant for me
- b) 1= It is very harmful to me, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7= It is very beneficial to me
- c) 1= It is completely useless to me, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7= It is very necessary to me
- d) 1= It is completely uninteresting to me, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6..., 7= It is very interesting to me
- e) 1= It is very stressful for me, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7= It is very relaxing for me
- f) 1= It upsets me a lot, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7= It pleases me a lot

21) Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 = Strongly disagree, ..., 7 = Strongly agree.

[matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) For you, a biocultural tourist experience in High Nature Value rural landscapes means the opportunity to learn about nature.
- b) For you, a biocultural tourist experience in High Nature Value rural landscapes means the opportunity to learn about traditions, the history of the place, and the local community.

- a) The people who are important to me believe that it is beneficial for me to visit High Nature Value rural landscapes for a biocultural tourist experience.
- b) The people who are important to me visit High Nature Value rural landscapes for a biocultural tourist experience.
- c) When I see that many people visit High Nature Value rural landscapes for a biocultural tourist experience, I will visit them as well.
- d) When public authorities support visiting High Nature Value rural landscapes for a biocultural tourist experience, I will visit them as well.

- a) I am responsible for learning more about how to protect biodiversity in High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- b) I consider that protecting High Nature Value rural landscapes is my moral responsibility.
- c) I feel that it is my responsibility to encourage others to engage in a biocultural tourist experience in High Nature Value rural landscapes.

- a) Human interaction with nature often has disastrous consequences.
- b) People must maintain balance with nature to survive.
- c) In Romania, the state of forests, pastures, protected areas, and High Nature Value rural landscapes is concerning.
- d) High Nature Value rural landscapes are viable examples and models for human-nature balance.
- e) The disappearance of ecological and traditional local knowledge in High Nature Value rural landscapes is concerning.
- f) The disconnection of people from nature in High Nature Value rural landscapes is accelerating.
- g) The state of nature in High Nature Value rural landscapes is closely linked to the cultural identity of the local community.
- h) Nature is an inseparable part of values, knowledge, folklore, and culture in general in the local communities of High Nature Value rural landscapes.

22) Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 = Strongly disagree, ..., 7 = Strongly agree.

[matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) I trust that I can have a biocultural tourist experience in High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- b) It depends on me to have a biocultural tourist experience in High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- c) For me, it is easy to have a biocultural tourist experience High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- d) I have all the necessary conditions (money, time, transportation, information) to have a biocultural tourist experience in High Nature Value rural landscapes.

23) Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 = Strongly disagree, ..., 7 = Strongly agree.

[matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) High Nature Value rural landscapes are important for the local community living there.
- b) High Nature Value rural landscapes are important for Romanian citizens in general.
- c) Being present in High Nature Value rural landscapes helps me connect with people (social cohesion).
- d) Caring for the ecosystems in High Nature Value rural landscapes is an essential part of my care for the people living in these landscapes (present and future residents) (social responsibility).
- e) Taking care of all forms of life is a moral necessity for me (moral responsibility towards non-humans).
- f) High Nature Value rural landscapes are important to me, for what I am as a person (individual identity).
- g) My concern for High Nature Value rural landscapes fulfils me and helps me lead a good life (Stewardship eudaimonic).
- h) Maintaining the health of High Nature Value rural landscapes is the right thing to do (principle/value of stewardship) Values

24) What is the maximum amount you would be willing to pay for a biocultural tourist experience in a High Nature Value rural landscape? [one choice]

- a) 500 RON per night per person
- b) 450 RON per night per person
- c) 400 RON per night per person
- d) 350 RON per night per person
- e) 300 RON per night per person
- f) 250 RON per night per person
- g) 200 RON per night per person
- h) 150 RON per night per person
- i) 100 RON per night per person
- j) Less than 100 RON per night per person
- k) I do not want to pay to visit a High Nature Value rural landscape

25) Indicate how willing you are to visit a High Nature Value rural landscape that offers a biocultural tourist experience in the next 12 months.

[one choice]

1 = Not at all willing to do this, ..., 7 = Very willing to do this

26) I intend to visit a High Nature Value rural landscape that offers a biocultural tourist experience in the next 12 months.

1 = Strongly disagree, ..., 7 = Strongly agree [one choice]

27) I plan to visit a High Nature Value rural landscape that offers a biocultural tourist experience in the next 12 months.

1 = I definitely will not plan to do this, ..., 7 = I definitely will plan to do this [one choice]

28) I will make all the preparations to visit a High Nature Value rural landscape that offers a biocultural tourist experience in the next 12 months.

1 = Definitely will not do this, ..., 7 = Definitely will do this [one choice]

29) How likely is it that you will visit a High Nature Value rural landscape for a biocultural tourist experience in the next 12 months?

1 = Definitely not, ..., 7 = Definitely yes [matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) One day (without accommodation)
- b) One night
- c) Two nights
- d) Three nights
- e) More than three nights

Biodiversity = all life types found in a given area. It encompasses the variety of animals, plants, fungi, and even microorganisms such as bacteria that make up our natural world. Each of these species and organisms works together in ecosystems, like a complex network, to maintain balance and support life. Biodiversity supports everything we need from nature in order to survive: food, clean water, health remedies, and shelter. Biodiversity also includes less visible aspects such as genes, plant varieties, or animal breeds produced through cultural selection throughout history. The diversity of ecosystems, landscapes, and, not least, the diversity of High Nature Value rural landscapes also falls under the category of biodiversity.

30) What do you think is the current state of biodiversity in High Nature Value rural landscapes in Romania? [one choice]

1= Very poor, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7= Very good

31) What do you think is the short-term trend (between 1 and 10 years) of the state of biodiversity in High Nature Value rural landscapes: [one choice]

1= It will worsen significantly compared to the current state, 2, 3, 4= It will remain as it is now, 5, 6, 7= It will improve significantly compared to the current state

32) What do you think is the long-term trend (more than 10 years) of the state of biodiversity in High Nature Value rural landscapes: [one choice]

1= It will worsen significantly compared to the current state, 2, 3, 4= It will remain as it is now, 5, 6, 7= It will improve significantly compared to the current state

33) To what extent do you think the current development of rural infrastructure in Romania (roads, lighting networks, gas, water, public utility buildings such as kindergartens, health centers) influences the protection of nature in High Nature Value rural landscapes? [one choice]

1= Very high negative influence, 2, 3, 4=No influence, 5, 6, 7= Very high positive influence

34) What do you think is the short-term trend (up to 10 years) of the state of rural traditions and rural communities in High Nature Value rural landscapes: [one choice]

1= It will worsen significantly compared to the current state, 2, 3, 4= It will remain as it is now, 5, 6, 7= It will improve significantly compared to the current state

35) What do you think is the long-term trend (more than 10 years) of the state of rural traditions and rural communities in High Nature Value rural landscapes: [one choice]

1= It will worsen significantly compared to the current state, 2, 3, 4= It will remain as it is now, 5, 6, 7= It will improve significantly compared to the current state

36) Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 = Strongly disagree, ..., 7 = Strongly agree.

[matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) The socio-cultural, economic, and natural values in High Nature Value rural landscapes are closely interconnected and should be addressed together to ensure a sustainable future for these landscapes.
- b) The socio-cultural, economic, and natural values in High Nature Value rural landscapes can be supported through enhanced educational and cultural quality as well as innovation within these landscapes.
- c) The socio-cultural, economic, and natural values in High Nature Value rural landscapes can be supported solely by creating economic opportunities for local residents, regardless of the nature of these activities.
- d) The socio-cultural, economic, and natural values in High Nature Value rural landscapes can be supported through political will.
- e) The socio-cultural, economic, and natural values in High Nature Value rural landscapes are jeopardized by the migration of young people from villages.
- f) The intensification and expansion of modern agriculture pose a threat to the nature-culture-tradition unity of High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- g) Local communities in High Nature Value rural landscapes are currently strong and cohesive, as they were traditionally.
- h) Local communities in many High Nature Value rural landscapes are undergoing dramatic social changes, which impact their cultural and local identity.
- i) The loss of cultural identity in communities within High Nature Value rural landscapes means the loss of universal heritage values.
- j) The authentic cultural identity of communities in High Nature Value rural landscapes is a feature that attracts me as a tourist.
- k) I consider that High Nature Value rural landscapes are largely characterized by the poverty of local residents, lack of education, and limited cultural and economic opportunities.

37) To what extent do you believe that the current development of rural infrastructure in Romania (such as roads, lighting networks, gas, water, and public utility buildings like kindergartens and health centres) influences the preservation of rural heritage (including traditional houses, bridges, churches, the local community's desire to preserve them, traditions, etc.)? [one choice]

1= Very high negative influence, 2, 3, 4=No influence, 5, 6, 7= Very high positive influence

38) Indicate your level of agreement with the following statements on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 = Strongly Disagree, ..., 7 = Strongly Agree.

[matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) Continuous soil tillage in High Nature Value rural landscapes is harmful to the "health" of the soil.
- b) Excessive use of groundwater in High Nature Value rural landscapes will cause a future water crisis for irrigation in that area.
- c) Excessive use of heavy motorized equipment for soil tillage in High Nature Value rural landscapes results in increased greenhouse gas emissions and thus exacerbates climate change.
- d) Intensive use of chemical substances in conventional agriculture in High Nature Value rural landscapes increases soil, water, and air pollution.
- e) Intensification and expansion of modern agriculture pose a threat to the nature-culture-tradition unity of High Nature Value rural landscapes.

39) Which of the following factors currently exist and contribute to the loss of biodiversity in High Natural Value rural landscapes? Please respond on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 = This factor does not contribute at all to the loss of biodiversity in High Natural Value rural landscapes, ..., 7 = This factor contributes significantly to the loss of biodiversity in High Natural Value rural landscapes. [matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) Corruption
- b) Laws changing too frequently
- c) Lack of legislation protecting High Natural Value rural landscapes
- d) Lack of enforcement of legislation regarding High Natural Value rural landscapes
- e) Lack of interest from locals
- f) Lack of interest from public authorities
- g) Poverty of locals
- h) Lack of knowledge among authorities about the role of High Natural Value rural landscapes
- i) Lack of knowledge among locals about the role of High Natural Value rural landscapes
- j) Disappearance of traditional agricultural knowledge about conserving High Natural Value rural landscapes
- k) Rural depopulation (migration from rural areas)
- l) Tourism
- m) Industrial activities
- n) Urbanization
- o) Intensive agriculture
- p) Climate change
- q) Loss of biodiversity
- r) Pollution

s) Other factors. Please mention them:.....

40) A factor can have both a positive and a negative influence. If you feel that some of the factors mentioned above currently have (also) a positive effect, helping to conserve High Nature Value rural landscapes, please select from the list below those that have a positive effect:
[multiple choice]

- a) Corruption
- b) Laws changing too frequently
- c) Lack of legislation protecting High Natural Value rural landscapes
- d) Lack of enforcement of legislation regarding High Natural Value rural landscapes
- e) Lack of interest from locals
- f) Lack of interest from public authorities
- g) Poverty of locals
- h) Lack of knowledge among authorities about the role of High Natural Value rural landscapes
- i) Lack of knowledge among locals about the role of High Natural Value rural landscapes
- j) Disappearance of traditional agricultural knowledge about conserving High Natural Value rural landscapes
- k) Rural depopulation (migration from rural areas)
- l) Tourism
- m) Industrial activities
- n) Urbanization
- o) Intensive agriculture
- p) Climate change
- q) Loss of biodiversity
- r) Pollution
- s) Other factors.

41) What other factors do you think can help conserve High Nature Value rural landscapes? [open]

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42) Who can contribute to improving biodiversity in High Nature Value rural landscapes? Please evaluate each factor on a scale from 1 to 7, where: 1 = This factor cannot contribute at all to improve biodiversity in High Nature Value rural landscapes, ..., 7 = This factor can contribute a lot to improve biodiversity in High Nature Value rural landscapes. [matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) The local community, in general

- b) Farmers
- c) Tourists
- d) The business community and industry
- e) Scientists
- f) The general public
- g) NGOs
- h) Local public authorities
- i) Central public authorities
- j) Minorities (ethnic, religious, etc.)
- k) Poor people
- l) Others. Please mention them:

43) How well do the statements below reflect what you will do in the near future (within the next 12 months) if the opportunity arises? Please respond on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 = I will definitely not do this, ..., 7 = I will definitely do this [matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) I will donate a sum of money for activities that protect High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- b) I will participate in activities to clean up High Nature Value rural landscapes to help protect them.
- c) I will vote for political candidates (at the local and central levels) who support the protection of High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- d) I will sign a petition for the implementation of stricter laws to protect High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- e) I will get involved in economic and cultural initiatives that support local communities and nature in High Nature Value rural landscapes.
- f) During my biocultural tourist experience in villages near High Nature Value rural landscapes, I will leave my car at the accommodation and walk, cycle, take a cart, or use motorized transportation provided by the local community.
- g) As a tourist in High Nature Value rural landscapes, I will camp only in permitted areas.

- a) As a tourist in High Nature Value rural landscapes, I will seek to stay within the local community.
- b) As a tourist in High Nature Value rural landscapes, I agree to contribute to social equity by paying a fair price for accommodation, buying local products, etc.
- c) As a tourist in High Nature Value rural landscapes, I seek to enjoy authentic local products, customs, and culture.
- d) Poverty, lack of education, and lack of cultural and economic opportunities in High Nature Value rural landscapes make me visit these areas rarely or not at all.

44) How important is it for you to support farmers and local communities when you have a biocultural tourist experience in a High Nature Value rural landscape? Please respond on a scale from 1 to 7, where 1 = Not important at all, ..., 7 = Very important. [one choice]

1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7

45) Which of the following statements are true and which are false? You can select multiple options. Choose the ones you think are true. [multiple choice]

- a) High Nature Value rural landscapes are located in rural areas where traditional agriculture is the main economic activity and a key factor in nature conservation.
- b) High Nature Value rural landscapes provide a livelihood for many communities in Romania.
- c) High Nature Value rural landscapes offer a rich heritage in terms of agricultural and culinary traditions and customs.
- d) High Nature Value rural landscapes ensure clean air, water, soil, and the protection of biodiversity.
- e) Protecting High Nature Value rural landscapes does not depend on the continuation of traditional agricultural practices.
- f) Intangible values (aesthetic, cultural, historical) are as important as tangible values (wood, agricultural products, etc.) in High Nature Value rural landscapes.

46) To what extent can a biocultural tourist experience in a High Nature Value rural landscape achieve the following? Please respond on a scale from 1 to 7, where: 1 = Does not help at all... 7 = Helps a lot [matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) Contributes to the protection of nature: air, water, soil, and biodiversity.
- b) Helps traditions and other elements of local culture (historical sites, traditional products) stay alive.
- c) Economically supports the local community.

47) To what extent can High Nature Value rural landscapes provide the following services? Please respond on a scale from 1 to 7, where: 1 = High Nature Value rural landscapes have very low capacity to provide this service, ..., 7 = High Nature Value rural landscapes have very high capacity to provide this service. [matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) Providing food for people
- b) Providing wild products (foraging fruits, berries, flowers, mushrooms)
- c) Supporting air quality
- d) Supporting climate
- e) Pollination
- f) Maintaining soil fertility
- g) Recreation and tourism
- h) Aesthetic service (beauty of landscapes)
- i) Cognitive development service (education, research)
- j) Social interactions (provides space for spending time with others)
- k) Inspirational values (produces feelings, new thoughts, religious or spiritual meanings)

48) How much trust do you have in the authenticity of the biocultural tourist experience offered in the community within a High Nature Value rural landscape? In other words, do you trust that the food is made from local products, prepared according to traditional recipes, the customs are local, the natural landscape features regional species, etc.? [one choice]

1= I have no trust at all, ..., 7= I have complete trust

49) To what extent do you believe that integrating sustainable agricultural practices into the agricultural system of a High Nature Value rural landscape would improve the sustainability of that region? In this context, when we talk about sustainability, we refer to improving the quality of life for the community, the state of the natural environment, and economic well-being. [one choice]

1= Would not improve sustainability at all... 7= Would improve sustainability very much

50) How important do you think policies and legal regulations are for encouraging the adoption of appropriate agricultural practices for High Nature Value lands in a High Nature Value rural landscape? [one choice]

1= Not important at all... 7= Very important

51) To what extent do you believe that collaboration between farmers, researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders is necessary for the successful integration of agricultural practices specific to High Nature Value rural landscapes into the broader agricultural system? [one choice]

1= Collaboration does not help at all... 7= Collaboration helps a lot

52) How important do you think the involvement of various stakeholders, including farmers, researchers, policymakers, and consumers, is for developing innovative and sustainable agricultural practices in High Nature Value rural landscapes? [one choice]

1= Not important at all... 7= Very important

53) To what extent do you believe that promoting cultural diversity and traditional agricultural knowledge in High Nature Value rural landscapes can contribute to the resilience of these landscapes in the face of environmental and socio-economic changes? [matrix; one choice for each line]

1= Does not contribute at all... 7= Contributes a lot

a) in the face of environmental changes

b) in the face of socio-economic changes

54) How important do you consider the role of farmers should be in influencing the development of policies and conservation practices for High Nature Value rural landscapes? [one choice]

1= Not important at all... 7= Very important

55) Which of the following do you consider necessary to support farmers in playing an active role in influencing the development of policies and conservation practices for High Nature Value rural landscapes? [matrix; one choice for each line]

1= Not important at all... 7= Very important

- a) Farmers' associations
- b) Legislation and administrative procedures that are easy to understand and implement
- c) Support from local and central public authorities (e.g., opportunities to express opinions, timely feedback)
- d) Educational and informational programs related to the role of farmers, the consequences of their non-involvement, acquiring negotiation skills, or examples of best practices from other communities
- e) Financial support for agricultural activities to enable involvement in these non-agricultural activities
- f) Others. Please specify.....

56) Whose opinions are important for the development of policies and practices for protecting High Nature Value rural landscapes? Indicate the importance of each on a scale from 1 to 7, where: 1 = Not important at all, ..., 7 = Very important [matrix; one choice for each line]

- a) The local community, in general
- b) Farmers
- c) Tourists
- d) The business and industry communities
- e) Scientists
- f) The general public
- g) NGOs
- h) Local public authorities
- i) Central public authorities
- j) Minorities (ethnic, religious, sexual, etc.)
- k) Poor people
- l) Others. Please specify whom you have in mind:

57) From the categories listed above, name 3 categories that you believe the most important to be considered in the development of policies and practices for the conservation of High Nature Value rural landscapes and which are currently overlooked.

Choose from the following or name others: Local community, in general; Farmers; Tourists; Business and industry communities; Scientists; The general public; NGOs; Minorities; Poor people; Local public authorities; Central public authorities. [open answer]

.....

58) To what extent do you believe that efforts to mobilize the population, such as involvement in the local community and other forms of activism (e.g., signing petitions, participating in public debates), can help raise public awareness about the conservation and promotion of High Nature Value rural landscapes and make these landscapes a more important issue in political discourse and decision-making? [one choice]

1= Does not help at all, ..., 7= Helps a lot

Gender [one choice]

1=F 2=M

Age:

Education (highest level completed or currently pursuing): [one choice]

- a) Up to 4 years of school
- b) Between 5-8 years of school
- c) Between 9-12 (or 13) years of school
- d) Bachelor's degree
- e) Master's degree
- f) Doctorate

Your income (net average monthly) : [one choice]

- a) Up to 2 500 RON/ month
- b) 2 501-5 000 RON/ month
- c) 5 000-10 000 RON/ month
- d) 10 001-15 000 RON/ month
- e) 15 001-20 000 RON/ month
- f) Over 20 000 RON/ month

County where you live:

Residential area: [one choice]

1= Urban 2= Rural